

THE INFLUENCE OF BRAND AWARENESS AND PRODUCT QUALITY ON REPURCHASE INTENTION OF MS GLOW SKINCARE PRODUCTS : MEDIATED BY BRAND TRUST

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Received : 10 February 2026

Accepted : 12 March 2026

Revised : 20 February 2026

Published : 23 March 2026

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intention of MS Glow skincare products with brand trust as a mediating variable. This study used a quantitative approach with a survey method of 120 students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Tadulako University who have used MS Glow products. Sampling was carried out using a purposive sampling technique. Data analysis used Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) through the SmartPLS application. The results of the study indicate that brand awareness and product quality have a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. In addition, brand awareness and product quality also have a positive and significant effect on brand trust. However, brand trust does not have a significant effect on repurchase intention and is unable to mediate the influence of brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intention. This study provides theoretical contributions to marketing studies as well as practical implications for companies in formulating marketing strategies that focus on strengthening brand awareness and improving product quality.

Keywords: *Brand Awareness; Product Quality; Brand Trust; Repurchase Intention; Ms Glow*

INTRODUCTION

skincare industry in Indonesia has experienced very rapid development in recent years, making it one of the most promising fields in the business world. Today, consumers no longer view skincare as a secondary need, but as an integral part of their daily lifestyle. Amidst intense competition in the skincare industry, companies are competing to promote superior product quality, ensuring their products are superior and superior to those of their competitors (Murniasih and Telagawathi, 2023). The use of skincare is not only intended to improve physical appearance but is also related to the need for impression management, namely the individual's efforts to manage the impression presented to the social environment (Robertson and Kingsley, 2021). Companies must not only sell products with claimed benefits but also be able to build consumer trust, maintain consistent quality, and build emotional connections with their target market. Brands that cannot adapt to changing consumer preferences and expectations in a highly competitive environment risk losing market share. MS Glow is a beauty brand under the auspices of PT. Kosmetika Cantik Indonesia. Established in 2013, MS Glow is an abbreviation of Magic For Skin. The presence of MS Glow in Palu City is clearly visible, one of its official branches is located on Jalan Gajah Mada, Siranindi, West Palu District. In addition to physical stores, MS Glow is also active in selling products online through social media and e-commerce platforms that expand product access for the community in Palu City, including students (MS Glow Indonesia, 2026).

Merek Skincare	Pangsa Pasar
Skintific	4,10%
Wardah	2,97%
Glad2Glow	2,51%
Hanasul	1,52%
Maybelline NY	1,47%
MS Glow	1,36%
Somehinc	1,23%
Skin1004	0,98%
Make Over	0,98%
Garnier	0,85%

Source: GoodStats Data (2025)

Figure 1. 10 Best-Selling Skincare Brands in Indonesia 2025

MS Glow's inclusion as one of the ten best-selling brands demonstrates that Indonesian-made products are as competitive as foreign brands. While its market share may not be as high as the top five, MS Glow's position below the top five does not reflect a decline in market interest, but rather demonstrates the intense competitive dynamics in the Indonesian skincare industry. MS Glow remains considered to have competitive product quality, enabling it to build and maintain brand trust in the minds of consumers. This brand trust plays a crucial role in driving repurchase intentions, particularly among consumers who have had positive product experiences. With increasingly competitive market conditions, MS Glow is a relevant object for examining the relationship between brand awareness, product quality, brand trust, and repurchase intentions, as this brand represents the dynamics of skincare consumer behavior in Indonesia in the current period.

When a brand sticks in consumers' minds, the likelihood of repurchase increases. In the context of intense competition in the local skincare industry, brand awareness is a crucial asset for differentiating MS Glow from other brands. Brand awareness relates to the level of consumer recognition of a particular brand, thus distinguishing it from competing brands in the same product category (Amalia et al., 2025). However, it should be noted that high awareness alone does not necessarily guarantee repurchase intention, as this also needs to be influenced by perceived product quality and consumer trust in the brand. To achieve the desired product quality, quality standardization is necessary. This method aims to ensure that the resulting product meets established standards so that it is appropriate for the target market segment (Caniago and Rustanto, 2022). Furthermore, if consumers have experienced the quality of the product they need, it will increase their interest in making a purchase decision. On the other hand, if the product quality does not meet expectations, this can reduce trust and discourage repeat purchases, even if consumers are familiar with the brand or influenced by advertising.

This quality aspect is closely related to brand trust, as positive experiences with a product will strengthen consumers' perception of the brand's reliability. Therefore, product quality must be well-maintained, not only during initial promotion but also in the long term. Consumers tend to trust brands they are already familiar with or exposed to on social media. Brand trust should not be taken for granted, especially for skincare products that are applied directly to the face and can experience adverse reactions if they are not suitable (Hastari et al., 2022). When trust in a brand is high, consumers will be more loyal and tend to make purchases comprehensively, not comparing with other brands, and often even repurchasing regularly. Consumers' growing trust in domestic products also marks a significant shift in how people choose skincare products. A company's success in building and maintaining positive consumer perceptions of its brand is key to driving repeat purchase intentions. In other words, repeat purchase intentions are influenced by elements within a marketing strategy, including brand trust, brand awareness, and product quality. All three contribute to building long-term relationships between consumers and brands. If customers are satisfied and trust a brand, they will have repeat purchase intentions (Utomo et al., 2023). In accordance with the explanation above, the purpose of this study is to examine the role of brand trust in mediating the relationship between brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intention of MS Glow skincare products among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Tadulako University. This study was conducted by examining the relationship between the independent variable, the mediating variable, and the dependent variable to determine its significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand Awareness

Kotler et al., (2022) state that building awareness involves developing consumers' ability to recognize or recall a brand in sufficient detail to ultimately decide to make a purchase. This describes the extent to which customers recognize a brand and how quickly the brand comes to mind when thinking about a particular type of product (Talahatu, 2024). Consumers tend to choose well-known brands because they feel more confident and secure with familiar products. According to Herawati et al., (2023), high brand awareness can foster associations attached to a brand. Consumers will also feel familiar with the brand, resulting in a feeling of liking. In addition, consumers will choose the brand as their primary option without much thought. This shows that high brand awareness can form positive associations for a product. Sutedjo and Yulia (2023) state that brand awareness is a buyer's ability to recognize and recall that a brand is part of a particular product category. In the context of the local skincare industry, MS Glow is a brand with a fairly strong level of brand awareness among consumers, characterized by its ability to be recognized and remembered as part of the skincare product category. Consumers who are familiar with this brand are more likely to choose MS Glow products than lesser-known brands (Mukti and Lestari, 2021). The brand awareness dimension in this study refers to Lembayung et al., (2023). Brand recognition, brand recall, and top of mind.

Product Quality

The quality of a product can describe how a product is made, what raw materials are used in making the product and what benefits consumers can get when purchasing the product (Darsana et al., 2023). Good quality is seen in goods that not only fulfill their basic functions but also provide comfort, satisfaction, and a pleasant experience when used. The American Society for Quality in Armstrong and Kotler (2023), defines quality as the characteristics of a product or service that are related to its ability to satisfy stated or implied customer needs. Armstrong and Kotler (2023) argue that a product is anything that can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use, or consumption that might satisfy a want or need. The existence of a product in the market is not only intended to create an image and build trust through aspects of quality, innovation, and suitability to ever-changing needs. This view suggests that a product's success can be measured by the level of additional benefits perceived by consumers. The greater the value offered, the greater the likelihood of consumer satisfaction and loyalty to the product. According to Pasaribu (2022), product quality is the ability of a product to display its function, this includes the product's useful life, reliability, ease of use and repair, and other values. MS Glow is perceived by consumers as a brand with good product quality, as reflected in the product's ability to deliver benefits according to consumer expectations (Qiamuddin and Kramadibrata, 2023). The product quality dimensions in this study refer to Garvin in Aziz et al., (2024). performance, durability, conformance to specifications, features, reliability, aesthetics, perceived quality.

Brand Trust

Brand trust is defined as a consumer's willingness to trust or rely on a brand in a risky situation due to the expectation that the brand will deliver positive results (Armanto et al., 2022). Brand trust is built on brand consistency in keeping promises, goodwill for consumer well-being, and the company's commitment to its core values. This definition reflects three important components that are interconnected in creating a positive perception: the first is consistent performance in providing quality products and services, the second is integrity in fulfilling promises, and the third is attention to consumer needs. This trust is formed because of the belief that others will behave according to what consumers need and want. MS Glow is perceived by consumers as a brand that has a good level of brand trust, primarily due to consumer confidence in the reliability of the product and the suitability of the perceived benefits with the claims conveyed by the brand (Sari and Risal, 2024). The dimensions of brand trust in this study refer to Khalis et al., (2022). dimension of viability and dimension of intentionality.

Repurchase Intention

According to Wanda and Susanto (2024), repurchase intention is a consumer's desire to make a repeat purchase in the future. Meanwhile, according to Wuisan et al., (2020), repurchase intention is a customer's desire and action to purchase a product, due to the emergence of customer satisfaction as expected from a product. Repurchase intention is defined as the actual behavior of customers that results in purchasing the same product or service more than once. The tendency of consumers to repurchase the same product or brand in the future after having a previous purchase experience. MS Glow is perceived by consumers as a brand that has a fairly high

repurchase intention, which is reflected in the tendency of consumers to repurchase the product after obtaining a positive usage experience (Anggriani and Ismunandar, 2022) . The dimensions of repurchase intention in this study refer to Wijaya and Tjahjaningsih (2022) , namely, transactional value, referential value, and exploratory value.

Hypothesis Development

1. Brand awareness reflects consumers' ability to recognize and recall a brand when faced with a particular product category (Ramadayanti, 2025) . Brands with a high level of awareness are more easily trusted because they create a sense of familiarity and reduce consumer uncertainty. Kotler et al., (2022) stated that consumers tend to trust well-known brands over less familiar ones. Research by Putriana and Abdurrahman (2024) also proved that brand awareness has a positive effect on brand trust. Thus, the higher the brand awareness of MS Glow, the higher the consumer trust in the brand.

H1: Brand awareness has a positive effect on brand trust.

2. Product quality indicates a product's ability to meet consumer needs and expectations, both in terms of performance, safety, and perceived benefits (Prakasa et al., 2025) . Products with consistent quality will build confidence that the brand is reliable. Armstrong and Kotler (2023) stated that product quality is the main basis for forming brand trust. Research by Hastari et al., (2022) also showed that product quality has a positive and significant effect on brand trust. Therefore, good MS Glow product quality is expected to increase brand trust.

H2: Product quality has a positive effect on brand trust.

3. Brand awareness plays a crucial role in driving repurchase intention (Herawati et al., 2023) . High brand awareness makes a brand the primary choice in consumers' minds when making a purchase. Consumers tend to repeat purchases of familiar brands because they are perceived as safer and less risky (Rahmi et al., 2022) . Therefore, the higher consumer awareness of the MS Glow brand, the greater their intention to repurchase. Research by Hidayat and Sugiarto (2026) also states that high brand awareness can encourage consumers in making purchasing decisions. Consumers tend to choose brands that are well-known and well-remembered, which ultimately can shape their intention to repurchase.

H3: Brand awareness has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

4. Perceived product quality that meets consumer expectations will create a positive experience and satisfaction, thus encouraging consumers to make purchases because this pleasant experience influences repurchase intentions (Jimawan and Mahyuni, 2026) . According to Felderova and Yuliviona (2023), product quality is a major factor influencing repurchase intentions. Therefore, the better the quality of MS Glow products perceived by consumers, the higher their repurchase intentions.

H4: Product quality has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

5. Brand trust is a consumer's belief that a brand will deliver positive and reliable results (Yusuf et al., 2024) . Consumers who have high trust in a brand will feel safer and more confident about making repeat purchases. Simanjuntak and Situmorang (2025) stated that brand trust has a positive effect on repurchase intention. Therefore, the higher the consumer's trust in the MS Glow brand, the greater the consumer's tendency to make repeat purchases.

H5: Brand trust has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

6. High brand awareness can increase consumer trust because the brand is perceived as more credible and familiar (Rahmi et al., 2022) . This established trust then encourages consumers to make repeat purchases. Judijanto et al., (2024) stated that brand trust can act as a mediator in the relationship between marketing factors and repurchase intention. Therefore, brand trust is expected to mediate the effect of brand awareness on repurchase intention for MS Glow products.

H6: Brand trust mediates brand awareness on repurchase intention.

7. Good product quality will build consumer trust in the brand, because positive perceptions of quality encourage the belief that the brand is reliable, which in turn encourages consumer repurchase intentions for the product (Selvia et al., 2024) . Consumers who believe that a brand is capable of providing consistent quality are more likely to make repeat purchases. Research by Khalis et al., (2022) shows that product quality influences brand trust and impacts consumer loyalty. Therefore, brand trust is expected to mediate the effect of product quality on MS Glow repurchase intentions.

H7: Brand trust mediates product quality on repurchase intention.

Figure 2. Research Framework

In the research framework diagram above, the existing lines have different meanings, namely:

- A straight line indicates a direct influence between variables. In this study, brand awareness (X1) and product quality (X2) have a direct influence on brand trust (Z). Furthermore, brand awareness (X1), product quality (X2), and brand trust (Z) are also assumed to have a direct influence on repurchase intention (Y).
- The dotted line indicates the indirect effect through the mediating variable. The dotted line connecting brand awareness (X1) and product quality (X2) with repurchase intention (Y) through brand trust (Z) indicates that brand trust acts as a mediating variable in the relationship.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a quantitative method with a causal approach. According to Sugiyono (2023), quantitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to study specific populations or samples. Data collection uses research instruments, and data analysis is quantitative or statistical, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. Positivism views a reality, symptom, or phenomenon as something that can be classified, concrete, observable, measurable, relatively constant, and has a causal relationship. Meanwhile, causality is data that allows researchers to assess the causal relationship between two or more variables (Hair et al., 2021). The population of this study was students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Tadulako University, who use or have used MS Glow skincare. Students were selected as the population because they are active consumers capable of evaluating brands, product quality, and forming repurchase intentions (Ulya and Fusfita, 2025). The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling. According to Sugiyono (2023), Purposive sampling is a data source sampling technique based on specific considerations. These considerations include, for example, the person who is considered to be most knowledgeable about what we expect, or perhaps the person in power, making it easier for researchers to explore the object/social situation being studied. Data were collected through a questionnaire based on indicators of brand awareness, product quality, brand trust, and repurchase intention using a 1-5-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

To determine the sample size, the researcher referred to Hair et al., (2021:161) which is considered comparable and is considered to have produced reliable and valid findings. This consideration is also often given the number of subgroups to be examined and the minimum sample size per subgroup required to draw conclusions about each subgroup, a general rule of thumb is five respondents for each measured indicator. In this study, there are 24 indicators so the minimum sample size required is 24 times 5 resulting in 120 respondents. Validity and reliability tests were conducted using the SPSS application, while Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) data analysis through SmartPLS 4.0 to examine the relationship between variables and the role of mediating variables (Hair et al., 2021). This method was chosen because it is able to analyze complex models and does not require normally distributed data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Data Characteristics

The presentation of respondent characteristics in this study aims to provide a general overview of the profile of the respondents who are the objects of the study. Respondent characteristics presented include gender, age, pocket money income, study program, year of entry, frequency of product purchases, and the type of MS Glow

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products used. The presentation of these characteristics is important to ensure the respondents' suitability to the research criteria, namely students who have used MS Glow skincare products. In addition, information on respondent characteristics is used to understand the demographic background and consumption behavior of respondents who have the potential to influence the level of brand awareness, perception of product quality, brand trust, and repurchase intention for MS Glow products.

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Category Statement	Answer Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
Gender	Woman	96	80%
	Man	24	20%
	Total	120	100%
Age	<18 Years	2	1.70%
	18-20 Years	48	40%
	21-23 Years	69	57.50%
	23-29 Years	1	0.80%
	Total	120	100%
Income/Pocket Money	<1000000	14	11.70%
	1,000,000-2,000,000	49	40.80%
	3,000,000-4,000,000	50	41.70%
	>4,000,000	7	5.80%
	Total	120	100%
Study Program/Major	Accountancy	30	25%
	Management	62	51.70%
	Economic development	28	23.30%
	Total	120	100%
Year of Entry	2021	23	19.20%
	2022	46	38.30%
	2023	30	25
	2024	21	17.50%
	Total	120	100
Product Usage	<3 Months	16	13.30%
	3-6 Months	35	29.20%
	6-12 Months	40	33.30%
	>1 Year	29	24.20%
	Total	120	100%
Product	Facial Wash	22	18.30%
	Toner	10	8.30%
	Serum	26	21.8
	Day Cream	19	15.4
	Night Cream	20	16.7
	Sunscreen	23	19.5
Total	120	100%	

Source: Primary Data (2026)

All of these results were obtained from the most frequently asked questions by respondents who completed the research questionnaire. Based on the table, the majority of respondents were female (80%) with an age range of 21–23 years (57.5%). Most respondents had pocket money of Rp3,000,000–Rp4,000,000 per month (41.7%) and were from the Management Study Program (51.7%). Respondents were predominantly students from the class of 2022 (38.3%). In terms of user experience, the majority of respondents had used MS Glow products for 6–12 months (33.3%), with the most commonly used product type being serum (21.8%), indicating a fairly intensive user experience with MS Glow products. These findings indicate that respondents have quite intensive product usage experience, making it relevant to analyze the influence of brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intention with brand trust as a mediating variable.

Outer Loading

Outer loading is the correlation value between an indicator and a latent construct in the measurement model (outer model) in PLS-SEM analysis. According to Hair et al. (2021), the outer loading value is evaluated based on the coefficient magnitude and its statistical significance, with a general guideline of 0.70 or higher indicating that the indicator has an adequate contribution in measuring the construct.

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2026)
Figure 3. Outer Loading

The model shown in this figure illustrates the direct and indirect influences between variables, where brand awareness and product quality influence brand trust, which in turn influences consumer repurchase intention. Furthermore, brand awareness and product quality also have a direct influence on repurchase intention. This model illustrates how brand awareness and product quality play a role in shaping consumer repurchase intention, both directly and through brand trust as a mediating variable.

Convergent Validity Test

The table below is used to assess the extent to which each indicator represents the construct being measured. In PLS-SEM analysis, convergent validity is evaluated based on the outer loading value, where a value greater than 0.70 indicates that the indicator meets the criteria and makes a good contribution to the construct. According to Hair et al. (2021), a high outer loading value indicates that the indicator is relevant and appropriate in describing the construct being studied. Therefore, the convergent validity test aims to ensure that the research instrument has adequate measurement quality, making it feasible and reliable for use in subsequent stages of analysis.

Table 2. Convergent Validity Test

Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Loading Factor	
Brand Awareness (X1)	Brand Recognition	Brand recognition ability	0.818	
	Brand Recall	Brand recall ability	0.852	
	Top of Mind	Ability to remember brand characteristics	0.805	
	Performance		Results as per claims	0.833
			The product works well	0.833
	Durability	Effective for long-term use	0.833	
Product Quality (X2)	Conformance to Specifications	Safe for skin	0.872	
		Does not cause irritation	0.905	
	Features	Variants according to skin type	0.958	
		The content of superior ingredients is clear	0.995	
	Reliability	Consistent use results	0.958	
	Aesthetics	Attractive packaging	0.872	
		Comfortable texture and aroma	0.878	
	Perceived Quality	Perceived as high quality	0.856	
		Trusted by many users	0.812	
		Product as claimed	0.876	
Brand Trust (Z)	Viability	Products according to consumer needs	0.962	
	Intentionality	Provides a sense of security in use	0.938	
		Reliable brand	0.890	
Repurchase Intention (Y)	Transactional Intention	Intend to buy back	0.872	
		Reuse	0.855	
	Referential Intention	Recommend	0.890	
		Try another variant	0.853	
Exploratory Intentions	Looking for additional information	0.807		

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2026)

Based on the results of the convergent validity test conducted through the outer loading value, it was found that all indicators and constituent constructs in this study had outer loading values above 0.70, both for the first-level latent construct and the second-level latent construct. This indicates that each indicator and constituent dimension is able to reflect the construct being measured well. It can be concluded that all constructs in this study have met the convergent validity criteria and are declared suitable for use in further testing of the structural model.

Discriminant Validity Test: Fornel and Lacker

Discriminant validity testing is used to ensure that each construct in the model is truly distinct from one another and does not measure the same concept. Discriminant validity is important because it demonstrates that a construct has unique characteristics compared to other constructs, so that the analysis results do not experience overlapping meanings between variables. One approach used in discriminant validity testing is the Fornell and Larcker criterion, namely by comparing the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct with its correlation value with other constructs. A construct is said to have good discriminant validity if the square root of the AVE value is greater than the correlation between constructs. Through this test, researchers can ensure that each construct in the PLS-SEM model has clear conceptual differences and can be analyzed separately without any overlapping measurements.

Table 3. Results of Discriminant Validity Test (Fornel & Lacker Criteria)

	Brand Trust Z	Brand Awareness X1	Product Quality X2	Repurchase Intention Y
Brand Trust Z	0.917			
Brand Awareness X1	0.893	0.825		
Product Quality X2	0.982	0.929	0.876	
Repurchase Intention Y	0.777	0.934	0.831	0.857

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2026)

The results in the table show that several correlation values between constructs are greater than the square root of AVE, namely the correlation between Brand Trust (Z) and Product Quality (X2) of 0.982, the correlation between Brand Awareness (X1) and Product Quality (X2) of 0.929, and the correlation between Brand Awareness (X1) and Repurchase Intention (Y) of 0.934. Based on the Fornell–Larcker criteria, this condition indicates that discriminant validity has not been fully met. However, the high correlation between these constructs can be explained theoretically because brand awareness, product quality, and brand trust in the context of MS Glow skincare products have a close relationship in forming repurchase intentions. Overall, all variables have met the eligibility criteria for analysis in the next stage.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing is conducted to ensure that each indicator within a construct is capable of producing consistent measurements. According to Hair et al., (2021) , good reliability indicates that the items within a variable are interrelated and work stably in measuring the same concept . In PLS-SEM, reliability is assessed through Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (ρ_a), where high values indicate the instrument is reliable and suitable for use in analysis. Thus, reliability testing helps researchers ensure that the data obtained is of adequate quality before further model testing.

Table 4. Reliability Test

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Brand Trust Z	0.937	0.939	0.841
Brand Awareness X1	0.765	0.766	0.681
Product Quality X2	0.969	0.971	0.767
Repurchase Intention Y	0.910	0.912	0.735

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2026)

The reliability test results show that all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.70 and Composite Reliability values above 0.70, thus concluding that each construct has good internal consistency. Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs are above 0.50, indicating that each construct is able to explain the variance of its indicators well.

Inner Model

R-Square Test

The R-Square test for internal models is used to determine how much independent variables can explain the dependent variable in a research model. Menurut Hair et al. (2021) The R-Square value indicates how strongly some variables influence the predicted variable. The higher the value, the better the model's ability to explain the phenomenon being studied. Therefore, the R-Square test helps researchers understand how well the structural model works and whether the relationships between the tested variables have adequate predictive power.

Table 5. R-Square Test Results

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Brand Trust Z	0.968	0.967
Repurchase Intention Y	0.890	0.887

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2026)

These results indicate that Brand Awareness and Product Quality variables are able to explain 96.8% of the variation in changes in Brand Trust. Furthermore, the variables Brand Awareness, Product Quality, and Brand Trust are able to explain 89.0% of the variation in changes in Repurchase Intention of MS Glow Skincare Products . This indicates that the relationship between variables in the structural model (inner model) is appropriate and able to describe the research phenomenon with a high level of explanation.

Hypothesis Testing

According to Hair et al. (2021), hypothesis testing is used to determine whether the relationship between variables in a research model is truly supported by the data. Hypothesis testing is conducted to assess the significance of the influence between variables in the research model through the t-statistic and p-value. In PLS-SEM analysis, testing is performed by examining the path coefficient and its significance level. The relationship between variables is declared significant if the p-value is below 0.05, thus the hypothesis is accepted. Through this test, the developed structural model can be empirically validated and the research conclusions can be scientifically justified.

Table 6. Hypothesis Test Results

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Brand Awareness X1 -> Repurchase Intention Y	1,187	1.17	0.118	10,062	0.000
Brand Awareness X1 -> Brand Trust Z	-0.145	-0.14	0.056	2,572	0.011
Product Quality X2 -> Repurchase Intention Y	-0.273	-0.254	0.125	2,173	0.032
Product Quality X2 -> Brand Trust Z	1,117	1,113	0.053	21,214	0.000
Brand Trust Z -> Repurchase Intention Y	-0.472	-0.508	0.295	1,600	0.112
Brand Awareness X1 -> Brand Trust Z -> Repurchase Intention Y	0.068	0.08	0.069	0.998	0.320
Product Quality X2 -> Brand Trust Z -> Repurchase Intention Y	-0.527	-0.574	0.349	1,511	0.134

Source: SEM-PLS 4.0 (2026)

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing in the table above, it can be seen that some of the relationships between variables in this study show significant results, as indicated by t-statistics values greater than 1.96 and p-values smaller than 0.05. Brand awareness has a significant effect on repurchase intention, as does product quality. In addition, product quality is also proven to have a significant effect on brand trust. However, brand trust does not have a significant effect on repurchase intention. Furthermore, the results of the indirect effect test indicate that brand trust is unable to mediate the relationship between brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intention. Overall, these findings indicate that the research model is able to explain the direct relationship between variables, while the mediation relationship through brand trust has not been empirically proven.

DISCUSSION

This study provides an empirical overview of the relationship between brand awareness, product quality, brand trust, and repurchase intention among consumers of MS Glow skincare products . The analysis results indicate that most of the relationships between variables in this research model are significant, although some paths do not show statistically significant effects. Before testing the relationships between variables, this study first ensures the feasibility of the outer model through a reliability test. The test results show that all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values above the recommended minimum limit, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values that meet convergent validity criteria. This indicates that the research instrument has good internal consistency and is able to measure the constructs accurately. This is in line with Hair et al., (2021) , who stated that

a measurement model is considered feasible if the indicators demonstrate adequate reliability and validity. The results of the discriminant validity test indicate that several square root values of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are still lower than the correlation between constructs, especially for the constructs of brand awareness and brand trust. This finding indicates that consumer perceptions of MS Glow tend to be interrelated between the level of brand recognition and trust in the brand. This condition may occur because skincare consumers often form trust based on brand familiarity obtained through intensive exposure, recommendations, and usage experience, so that the boundaries between brand awareness and brand trust become relatively overlapping. The results of the hypothesis testing indicate that brand awareness significantly influences repurchase intention. This finding indicates that the higher the level of consumer recognition and recall of the MS Glow brand, the greater the consumer's tendency to repurchase. Theoretically, brand awareness increases consumer familiarity with the brand and reduces the perceived risk of repurchasing. This also aligns with research by Rahmi et al. (2022) , which states that brand awareness influences repurchase intention because consumers feel more confident in familiar brands.

However, the test results show a negative and significant relationship between brand awareness and brand trust. This finding suggests that higher consumer recognition of the MS Glow brand does not always translate into increased trust in the brand. This phenomenon can be explained by the high intensity of promotions on social media. Consumers often see MS Glow content, making the brand easily remembered and recognized. However, excessive exposure to promotions can raise doubts. Consumers may question whether the claims conveyed truly align with the actual experiences of product users (Kothari et al., 2025) . This finding is also in line with research conducted by Cheah et al., (2024) which states that excessive promotions on social media can reduce consumers' perceptions of credibility and trust in a brand, as consumers become skeptical of the marketing messages they receive. When consumers realize they are constantly being targeted by promotions, they tend to be more critical and less likely to immediately trust the information conveyed. Therefore, high brand awareness in this study has not been able to optimally build brand trust.

Furthermore, product quality was shown to have a significant effect on repurchase intention, but with a negative influence. This means that even though consumers rate product quality highly, this does not always make them want to repurchase the product. This result is in line with research by Ratnasari and Sudarman (2025) , who also found that the direct effect of product quality on repurchase intention can be negative in the research model. In the context of skincare products , results of use cannot be seen instantly. Consumers generally need time to observe long-term effects and ensure the product is suitable for their skin condition. This evaluation process makes consumers tend to be more cautious before deciding to repurchase (Hussin et al., 2025) . Furthermore, if consumers have very high expectations about product quality, then a mismatch between expectations and usage experience can influence their assessment of repurchase intention (Shukla et al., 2025) . In this study, product quality does include aspects of suitability for individual skin conditions, as measured by indicators such as safety for the skin, non-irritating, and variants suitable for skin type. However, although respondents generally perceived the product to be of good quality based on these indicators, individual user experiences can vary due to varying skin characteristics. Therefore, some consumers may still experience incompatibility, prompting them to discontinue use and switch to another product (George and Sony, 2024) .

Based on the test results, product quality has a positive and significant effect on brand trust. This finding indicates that consistent MS Glow product quality can build consumer confidence in the brand. Brand trust is formed when consumers believe the brand can fulfill its promises and deliver reliable results. This finding is supported by Aziz et al. (2024) , who stated that product quality is a key determinant in building brand trust in skincare. In contrast to other hypotheses, the results of the study indicate that brand trust does not significantly influence repurchase intentions. This finding supports the research results of Mutiah and Marliani (2024), which also showed that brand trust does not significantly influence repurchase intentions. Repurchase intention. According to Chairunisa et al., (2025) Brand trust can be high but repurchase intention is low because trust only ensures that the brand is safe and will not disappoint, but does not guarantee that the product is the best choice. To encourage repurchase intention, consumers need better benefits compared to other products. If the results are perceived as mediocre or not superior, consumers do not have a strong reason to repurchase, even though they still trust the brand. In addition, according to George and Sony (2024), Generation Z is known to have a tendency to try various new products and easily switch brands , even though they have experience and trust in previous brands. Thus, even though consumers have a good level of trust in the MS Glow brand, the urge to explore other products that are considered more interesting or trendy can reduce the tendency to make repeat purchases.

The results of the mediation effect test indicate that brand trust is unable to mediate the relationship between brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intention because the characteristics of respondents are dominated by Generation Z. Research by George and Sony, (2024) shows that Gen Z has a tendency to brand switch (switch brands) in skincare products. In the study it is explained that Gen Z easily switches brands if they find a product that better suits their preferences, influenced by trends, social media reviews, and influencer recommendations. Although brand awareness and product quality can increase brand trust, this trust is not strong enough to prevent the tendency to switch to another product. For Generation Z, trying new products is often more attractive than maintaining the use of the same product. As a result, brand trust only stops at the level of confidence in the safety and credibility of the product. Therefore, brand trust is unable to mediate the relationship between these variables. This is in line with the research of Anastasiei et al., (2025) which states that brand trust does not always play a role as a mediating variable in forming repurchase intention. The study proves that although brand trust was tested as a mediator, the test results were not significant, so that repurchase intention is more influenced by direct evaluation of product quality and perceived risk.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that brand awareness and product quality have a significant effect on consumer repurchase intentions for MS Glow skincare products. Brand awareness has a positive effect on repurchase intentions, which means that the higher the level of consumer recognition of the brand, the greater the tendency to make a repeat purchase. Product quality also has a significant effect on repurchase intentions, but with a negative influence direction. This shows that consumers tend to make more rational and careful evaluations before deciding to repurchase, especially for skincare products related to skin suitability. Meanwhile, brand trust does not have a significant effect on repurchase intentions and is unable to mediate the relationship between brand awareness and product quality on repurchase intentions.

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Theoretically, this study provides additional insight into marketing studies, particularly regarding the relationship between brand awareness, product quality, brand trust, and repurchase intention. The results indicate that brand trust does not always play a significant role in driving repurchase intention. This finding suggests that consumer behavior can differ depending on the characteristics of the respondents and the context of the product being studied. Therefore, this study demonstrates that the relationship between variables in marketing is not always fixed and can be influenced by certain conditions. Practically, the results of this study provide input for MS Glow to not only increase promotions to expand brand awareness but also ensure that product quality meets consumer needs and expectations. Consumers tend to be more cautious in repurchasing skincare products because they consider suitability and results. Therefore, the company needs to maintain consistent product quality, provide clear information about benefits and how to use, and build good communication with consumers through social media and digital platforms.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations. First, the study was conducted only on students from the Faculty of Economics and Business at Tadulako University, so the results cannot be generalized to a wider population. Second, the variables used in this study were limited to brand awareness, product quality, brand trust, and repurchase intention, indicating that other factors could influence repurchase intention. Third, this study used a survey method with a questionnaire, so respondents' answers depended on each individual's perception.

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